

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

Daniel Linhares Lim-Apo

¹University of Brasília (UnB), Department of Computer Science, Brasília, DF, Brazil
E-mail: daniel.unb@sede.com.br, ednacanedo@unb.br

Table 1. Privacy-preserving techniques identified in the SMS for textual data analysis (RQ.1).

Cluster A: Data Transformation-Based Privacy-Preserving Techniques	
Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Studies
Anonymization	[Yan et al. 2024, Singhofer et al. 2021, Weggenmann et al. 2022, van Staalduine and Zuiderwijk 2025, Stauffer et al. 2024, Chevrier et al. 2019, Henriksson et al. 2017, Gupta et al. 2024, Abdalla et al. 2020, Meystre et al. 2014]
Correlation Based Transformation Strategy (CBTS)	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Data Perturbation	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Data Removing	[Hassan et al. 2019]
Data Sanitization	[Weggenmann et al. 2022, Stauffer et al. 2024]
De-identification	[Chevrier et al. 2019, Cardinal 2017, Demner-Fushman et al. 2016, Henriksson et al. 2017, Abdalla et al. 2020, Obeid et al. 2019, Meystre et al. 2014, Mehta et al. 2019]
K-Anonymity	[Languré and Zareei 2025, Singhofer et al. 2021, Mehta et al. 2019]
l-diversity	[Mehta et al. 2019]
MapReduce-based Anonymization (MRA)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Microaggregation	[Yang et al. 2020]
Multidimensional k-anonymization	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Privacy Preserving Transformation Strategies (PPTS)	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Pseudonymization	[Yan et al. 2024, Volodina et al. 2023]
Rx-anon	[Singhofer et al. 2021]
t-closeness	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Top-Down Specialization (TDS)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Two-Phase Top-Down Specialization (TPTDS)	[Mehta et al. 2019]
Wavelet-Based Transformations	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Cluster B: Cryptographic Privacy-Preserving Techniques	
Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Studies
Cryptographic	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Encryption	[Hadj Ahmed et al. 2015, Yang et al. 2018, Aldeen et al. 2016]
Homomorphic Encryption	[Hadj Ahmed et al. 2015, Aldeen et al. 2016]
Cluster C: Statistical Privacy and Differential Privacy Privacy-Preserving Techniques	
Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Studies
Differential Privacy	[Feng et al. 2024, Hu et al. 2024, Yang et al. 2020, Bo et al. 2021]
Differential Privacy Protection Correlations between Attributes (DPPCA)	[Yang et al. 2020]
Mutual Information	[Yang et al. 2020]
SynTF	[Bo et al. 2021]
Cluster D: Federated and Distributed Learning Privacy-Preserving Techniques	
Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Studies
Federated Learning	[Guo et al. 2024, Liu et al. 2020, Lit et al. 2022, Han et al. 2025]
FedAdam	[Lit et al. 2022]
FedAvg	[Lit et al. 2022]
FedProx	[Lit et al. 2022]
FedSplitBERT	[Lit et al. 2022]
FL-based Gated Recurrent Unit Neural Network (FedGRU)	[Liu et al. 2020]

Cluster E: Semantic, Ontological, and Hybrid Techniques	
Privacy-Preserving Techniques	Studies
Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
Cloud Information Retrieval (CIR)	[Yang et al. 2018]
Local Keyphrase Dictionary	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Ontology Construction and Property Injection	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Semantic Transformations	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Semantic Weighted Context Tagging Engine	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Sensitive Data Corpus	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]
SOBA	[Nethravathi et al. 2016]
Specialized NLP Models	[Hu et al. 2024]
SPEDAC	[Gambarelli et al. 2023]

References

- Abdalla, M., Abdalla, M., Hirst, G., and Rudzicz, F. (2020). Exploring the Privacy-Preserving Properties of Word Embeddings: Algorithmic Validation Study. *JOURNAL OF MEDICAL INTERNET RESEARCH*, 22(7). Place: 130 QUEENS QUAY E, STE 1102, TORONTO, ON M5A 0P6, CANADA Publisher: JMIR PUBLICATIONS, INC Type: Article.
- Aldeen, Y. A. A. S., Salleh, M., and Aljeroudi, Y. (2016). An innovative privacy preserving technique for incremental datasets on cloud computing. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 62:107–116.
- Bo, H., Ding, S. H. H., Fung, B. C. M., and Iqbal, F. (2021). ER-AE: Differentially Private Text Generation for Authorship Anonymization. In Toutanova, K., Rumshisky, A., Zettlemoyer, L., Hakkani-Tur, D., Beltagy, I., Bethard, S., Cotterell, R., Chakraborty, T., and Zhou, Y., editors, *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, pages 3997–4007, Online. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Cardinal, R. N. (2017). Clinical records anonymisation and text extraction (CRATE): An open-source software system. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 17(1). Publisher: BioMed Central Ltd.
- Chevrier, R., Foufi, V., Gaudet-Blavignac, C., Robert, A., and Lovis, C. (2019). Use and Understanding of Anonymization and De-Identification in the Biomedical Literature: Scoping Review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 21(5):e13484. Company: Journal of Medical Internet Research Distributor: Journal of Medical Internet Research Institution: Journal of Medical Internet Research Label: Journal of Medical Internet Research Publisher: JMIR Publications Inc., Toronto, Canada.
- Demner-Fushman, D., Kohli, M. D., Rosenman, M. B., Shooshan, S. E., Rodriguez, L., Antani, S., Thoma, G. R., and McDonald, C. J. (2016). Preparing a collection of radiology examinations for distribution and retrieval. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 23(2):304–310.
- Feng, J., Yang, L. T., Ren, B., Zou, D., Dong, M., and Zhang, S. (2024). Tensor Recurrent Neural Network With Differential Privacy. *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, 73(3):683–693.
- Gambarelli, G., Gangemi, A., and Tripodi, R. (2023). Is Your Model Sensitive? SPEDAC: A New Resource for the Automatic Classification of Sensitive Personal Data. *IEEE Access*, 11:10864–10880.

- Guo, T., Guo, S., Wang, J., Tang, X., and Xu, W. (2024). PromptFL: Let Federated Participants Cooperatively Learn Prompts Instead of Models Federated Learning in Age of Foundation Model. *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, 23(5):5179–5194.
- Gupta, B. B., Gaurav, A., Arya, V., Alhalabi, W., Alsalman, D., and Vijayakumar, P. (2024). Enhancing user prompt confidentiality in Large Language Models through advanced differential encryption. *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 116:109215.
- Hadj Ahmed, B., Amine, A., and Reda Mohamed, H. (2015). New Private Information Retrieval Protocol Using Social Bees Lifestyle over Cloud Computing. In *2015 IEEE International Conference on Computational Intelligence & Communication Technology*, pages 161–165.
- Han, C., Yang, T., Cui, Z., and Sun, X. (2025). A Privacy-Preserving and Trustworthy Inference Framework for LLM-IoT Integration via Hierarchical Federated Collaborative Computing. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, pages 1–1.
- Hassan, F., Sánchez, D., Soria-Comas, J., and Domingo-Ferrer, J. (2019). Automatic Anonymization of Textual Documents: Detecting Sensitive Information via Word Embeddings. In *2019 18th IEEE International Conference On Trust, Security And Privacy In Computing And Communications/13th IEEE International Conference On Big Data Science And Engineering (TrustCom/BigDataSE)*, pages 358–365. ISSN: 2324-9013.
- Henriksson, A., Kvist, M., and Dalianis, H. (2017). Detecting Protected Health Information in Heterogeneous Clinical Notes. In *MEDINFO 2017: Precision Healthcare through Informatics*, pages 393–397. IOS Press.
- Hu, J., Bao, R., Lin, Y., Zhang, H., and Xiang, Y. (2024). Accurate Medical Named Entity Recognition Through Specialized NLP Models. In *2024 6th International Conference on Frontier Technologies of Information and Computer (ICFTIC)*, pages 578–582.
- Languré, A. d. L. and Zareei, M. (2025). Privacy-Preserving Emotion Detection: Evaluating the Trade-Off Between K-Anonymity and Model Performance. *IEEE Access*, 13:105901–105910.
- Lit, Z., Sit, S., Wang, J., and Xiao, J. (2022). Federated Split BERT for Heterogeneous Text Classification. In *2022 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, pages 1–8. ISSN: 2161-4407.
- Liu, Y., Yu, J. J. Q., Kang, J., Niyato, D., and Zhang, S. (2020). Privacy-Preserving Traffic Flow Prediction: A Federated Learning Approach. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7(8):7751–7763.
- Mehta, B., Rao, U. P., Gupta, R., and Conti, M. (2019). Towards privacy preserving unstructured big data publishing. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 36(4):3471–3482. Publisher: SAGE Publications.
- Meystre, S. M., Ferrández, ., Friedlin, F. J., South, B. R., Shen, S., and Samore, M. H. (2014). Text de-identification for privacy protection: A study of its impact on clinical text information content. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 50:142–150.
- Nethravathi, N. P., Rao, P. G., Desai, V. J., Shenoy, P. D., Venugopal, K. R., and Indiramma, M. (2016). SWCTE: Semantic weighted context tagging engine for privacy

- preserving data mining. In *2016 International Conference on Data Science and Engineering (ICDSE)*, pages 1–5.
- Obeid, J. S., Heider, P. M., Weeda, E. R., Matuskowitz, A. J., Carr, C. M., Gagnon, K., Crawford, T., and Meystre, S. M. (2019). Impact of De-Identification on Clinical Text Classification Using Traditional and Deep Learning Classifiers. In Ohno-Machado, L. and Seroussi, B., editors, *MEDINFO 2019: HEALTH AND WELLBEING E-NETWORKS FOR ALL*, volume 264 of *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics*, pages 283–287, NIEUWE HEMWEG 6B, 1013 BG AMSTERDAM, NETHERLANDS. IOS PRESS. Backup Publisher: French Assoc Med Informat ISSN: 0926-9630 Type: Proceedings Paper.
- Singhofer, F., Garifullina, A., Kern, M., and Scherp, A. (2021). A novel approach on the joint de-identification of textual and relational data with a modified mondrian algorithm. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM Symposium on Document Engineering, DocEng '21*, pages 1–10, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- Staufer, D., Pallas, F., and Berendt, B. (2024). Silencing the Risk, Not the Whistle: A Semi-automated Text Sanitization Tool for Mitigating the Risk of Whistleblower Re-Identification. In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, FAccT '24*, pages 733–745, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery.
- van Staalduine, N. and Zuiderwijk, A. (2025). Exploring the Viability of ChatGPT for Personal Data Anonymization in Government: A Comprehensive Analysis of Possibilities, Risks, and Ethical Implications. *Digit. Gov.: Res. Pract.*, 6(2). Place: New York, NY, USA Publisher: Association for Computing Machinery.
- Volodina, E., Dobnik, S., Tiedemann, T. L. m., and Vu, X.-S. (2023). Grandma Karl is 27 years old research agenda for pseudonymization of research data. In *2023 IEEE Ninth International Conference on Big Data Computing Service and Applications (Big-DataService)*, pages 229–233.
- Weggenmann, B., Rublack, V., Andrejczuk, M., Mattern, J., and Kerschbaum, F. (2022). DP-VAE: Human-Readable Text Anonymization for Online Reviews with Differentially Private Variational Autoencoders. In *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2022, WWW '22*, pages 721–731, New York, NY, USA. Association for Computing Machinery. event-place: Virtual Event, Lyon, France.
- Yan, B., Li, K., Xu, M., Dong, Y., Zhang, Y., Ren, Z., and Cheng, X. (2024). On Protecting the Data Privacy of Large Language Models (LLMs): A Survey. In *2024 International Conference on Meta Computing (ICMC)*, pages 1–12.
- Yang, G., Ye, X., Fang, X., Wu, R., and Wang, L. (2020). Associated Attribute-Aware Differentially Private Data Publishing via Microaggregation. *IEEE Access*, 8:79158–79168.
- Yang, Z., Tang, J., and Liu, H. (2018). Cloud Information Retrieval: Model Description and Scheme Design. *IEEE Access*, 6:15420–15430.